

FRETTING FATIGUE OF SHAFTS UNDER VARYING CONTACT PRESSURE AND CREEP SLIP CONDITIONS IN BEARING-SHAFT CONTACTS

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The shafts, used to transmit rotary motion in drive trains, often receive the dynamic load of rotating bending. The support of the shaft is normally realised with press fitted roller bearings. The elastic deflection during operation of the shaft leads to microslip movements in contact with the bearing inner ring, resulting in the phenomenon of fretting fatigue and thus failure of the shaft. The special characteristic of this connection is found on the one hand in the kinematics of the slip – besides a clearly reversing slip in axial direction when changing from bending tension to bending pressure, a creeping slip in circumferential direction occurs – and on the other hand in the cyclical change of the contact pressure – up to a gaping of the contact. For the determination of the fatigue limits of the connection, experimental investigations were first carried out in the high cycle fatigue domain. The material used for the shaft was C45+N. The material of the bearing inner ring was 100Cr6. At run-out specimen as well as at broken specimen the slip zones in axial direction resulting from the bending and in circumferential direction resulting from the creeping slipping of the bearing inner ring are visible. Numerical investigations were then carried out to determine the local stresses at the interface. Subsequently, a comparative strength study of integral and critical-plane approaches was carried out. The fretting fatigue strength was defined as a nonuniform function of pressure and slip at the interface.

Keywords: fretting fatigue, bearing seat, contact fatigue, variable contact pressure, multiaxial fatigue

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

In many cases, highly stressed shaft bearings are located at the output of the technical system, such as a rotor shaft bearing of a wind turbine. Due to their oversize and design, the bearings are considered to be interference fits with transmitted torque in high-cycle-fatigue domain. While the bearing strength is normally well represented by the manufacturer, the strength of the shaft takes priority at this position. In shaft design, the experimental notch coefficients for interference fits are often used in the fatigue calculations. Especially with bearing rings in particular, there are some differences compared to classic torque-transmitting interference fits. On the one hand, the nominal contact pressure is much lower and, due to the rolling loads over the entire interface, it has non-uniform and variable distribution over the load cycle.

The local stress below the bearing ring includes the multiaxial stress-mechanical component, which can be represented in the form of the transient stress tensor. In addition, tribological stresses such as slip and pressure occur in the joint, which of course influence the former, but it is known from past studies e.g. by Funk [1] and current studies by Knabner [2] that they can cause additional tribological

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crack damage. In order to be able to perform a stress analysis at this contact point, it is therefore necessary to correctly evaluate the prevailing non-proportional stress state as well as the quantitative consideration of the tribological influences described.

In this paper, corresponding tests are presented and numerically analysed using a shaft material and a bearing type as examples. The hypotheses and material properties used for this purpose are taken from the latest research results.

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Specimen geometry and material

In preparation for the experimental investigations, material tests were carried out for reversed fatigue limit s_{-1} . For the investigated material C45+N, the uniaxial fatigue limit in reversed mode was determined by use of staircase method according to DIN 50100 [3]. The characteristic values required for the subsequent strength assessment could be calculated using proven calculation methods. The mean stress sensitivity from the FKM guideline by Rennert [4] can be used for the conversion of the fatigue limit in repeated mode ($R = 0$):

$$s_0 = 2 \cdot s_{-1} / (1 - 0.35 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \sigma_{UTS} / \text{MPa} - 0.1) \quad (1)$$

The estimation of the reversed torsional fatigue limit t_{-1} can be done with the formula:

$$t_{-1} = s_{-1} \cdot F_\tau \quad (2)$$

The factor F_τ takes into account that the material can have a different strength ratio to Von Mises $F_\tau = t_{-1} / s_{-1} = 1 / \sqrt{3}$. Based on the experience of authors $F_\tau = 0.63$ was chosen. The torsional threshold strength can also be calculated very well using the formula from Liu (7):

$$t_0 = 4 \cdot \frac{t_{-1}}{2 \cdot \frac{s_{-1}}{s_0} + 1} \quad (3)$$

TABLE 1 shows the strength values determined for the material analysed.

TABLE 1 Material properties

shaft material	σ_Y (MPa)	σ_{UTS} (MPa)	E (MPa)	s_{-1} (MPa)	s_0 (MPa)	t_{-1} (MPa)	t_0 (MPa)
C45+N	370	675	205 566	262	230.6	165.1	154.5

The shaft specimen was manufactured by turning and grinding. The relative interference of $\xi = l/d = 0.3\text{‰}$ was ensured by precise measuring the diameter and pairing shafts and bearing rings. The components were joined by heating the bearing to 80°C and then fitting it into the intended axial position on the test shaft.

TABLE 2 Specimen specification

shaft properties		bearing properties	
<i>material</i>	C45+N (1.0503)	<i>material</i>	100Cr6 (1.3505)
<i>nominal diameter</i>	60 mm	<i>type</i>	22212E
<i>length</i>	710 mm	<i>Inner/outer diameter of the inner ring</i>	60/73
<i>interference</i>	0.018 mm	<i>length</i>	28

Test procedure

The rotating bending test rig developed at the authors’ institute was used for the bending moment transmission tests. The test rig’s design is shown in FIGURE 1. Basically, the test shafts are deflected by a pneumatic cylinder via a lever arm as a 3-point bending. The rotation is realised by turning the shaft with the use of a single drive motor. As a result, there is a rotating bending in the shaft. The load on the shaft is continuously monitored and controlled during the test using a load cell between the pneumatic cylinder and lever arm. Breakage of the test shafts is detected by deflection sensors near the test bearing. The shaft is installed in the test rig via three support bearing housings and connected to the motor via a flexible coupling.

FIGURE 1 Test setup

All tests were carried out using the staircase method in accordance with DIN 50100 [3]. The limit number of load cycles was 10 million load cycles. The termination criterion was the maximum deflection set shortly before the residual fracture due to test rig safety. The residual force fracture was carried out for some samples on an external device for analysis purposes. In addition, the samples were subjected to a magnetic crack test to analyse the fatigue crack progression.

CALCULATION METHODS

Finite element modelling

To simplify the model structure, only the bearing inner ring with shaft and the rolling elements are simulated. The shaft and bearing ring are modelled as elastic solid bodies and the rolling elements as rigid bodies (FIGURE 2). After the arrangement of the individual components in the overall model, the respective reference points of all rolling elements are coupled with a centric reference point (center point) using a shear joint (connector type "Translator"). This means that each rolling element only has one degree of freedom in the radial direction. This degree of freedom is then eliminated in the form of force boundary conditions (or rolling element loads). The coupling of this centric reference point with a node point of the shaft then enables the rolling elements to experience the same displacement as the shaft and the rolling bearing loads to be applied correctly.

FIGURE 2 Finite element model of the assembled specimen

The contact definition was set to penalty with coefficient of friction of $\mu = 0.5$ and elastic slip of $s_{elastic} = 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. The material was defined with elastic properties of $E = 205 \text{ GPa}$ and $\nu = 0.3$.

Strength assessment

The strength assessment is carried out by comparing the equivalent stress with the material specific reversed fatigue limit s_{-1} . As the test loads are integrated in the simulation in the present case, the ratio S of the fatigue limit and the equivalent stress σ_{eq} should be exactly $S = s_{-1}/\sigma_{eq} = 1$. For this purpose, the strength hypotheses, which perform very well in current benchmarks in the validations by Papuga [5] [6] are used. On the one hand, two integral criteria according to Zenner [7] and Böhme [8] were applied. The criteria using a critical plane method are Findley [9], McDiarmid [10] and QCP according to Papuga [11]. All criteria are listed in the following equations, their material parameters are summarised in the appendix

$$\sigma_{eq,SIH} = \sqrt{\frac{15}{8\pi} \int_{\varphi=0}^{2\pi} \int_{\psi=0}^{\pi} [a_{SIH} C_a^2 (1 + c_{SIH} C_m^2) + b_{SIH} N_a^2 (1 + d_{SIH} N_m)] \sin\psi \, d\psi \, d\varphi} \leq s_{-1} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{eq,BO1} = \sqrt{\frac{15}{8\pi} \int_{\varphi=0}^{2\pi} \int_{\psi=0}^{\pi} [(a_{BO1} C_a^2 + b_{BO1} N_a^2) (1 + c_{BO1} N_m)^2 + d_{BO1} C_a C_m] \sin\psi \, d\psi \, d\varphi} \leq s_{-1} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{eq,Findley} = a \cdot \tau_{Na} + b \cdot \sigma_{N,max} \leq s_{-1} \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{eq,McDiarmid} = a \cdot \tau_{Na} + \frac{s_{-1}}{2\sigma_{UMS}} \cdot \sigma_{N,max} \leq s_{-1} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_{eq,QCP} = \sqrt{a_{QCP} \cdot C_a (C_a + c_{QCP} \cdot C_m) + b_{QCP} \cdot N_a (N_a + d_{QCP} \cdot N_m)} \leq s_{-1} \quad (8)$$

Since the material strength can be determined for contacts in equivalent tensile test with fretting pads reversed fatigue limit s_{-1} can be replaced by the fretting fatigue limit σ_{FF} :

$$\sigma_{eq} \leq \sigma_{FF,worst} \quad (9)$$

As stated by Knabner [2] the fretting fatigue limit $\sigma_{FF,worst}$ can be conservatively assumed for worst tribological case of contact pressure $p = 40$ MPa and slip amplitude $s_a = 10$ μm .

The slip amplitude and the contact pressure are expected to be different in contact of the present bearing seat. For this reason, the fretting fatigue strength $\sigma_{FF,worst}$ is reformulated according to the curve from Knabner [2] as a function of the pressure and the slip (FIGURE 3). For this purpose, the material strength has been expressed as

$$\sigma_{FF}(s_a, p) = \begin{cases} (a_0 + a_1 \cdot s_a + a_2 \cdot p + a_3 \cdot s_a^2 + a_4 \cdot s_a \cdot p + a_5 \cdot p^2 + a_6 \cdot s_a^2 \cdot p + a_7 \cdot s_a \cdot p^2 + a_8 \cdot p^3) \cdot s_{-1}; & p < 40 \text{ MPa} \\ (a_9 + a_{10} \cdot s_a + a_{11} \cdot p + a_{12} \cdot s_a^2 + a_{13} \cdot s_a \cdot p) \cdot s_{-1}; & p \geq 40 \text{ MPa} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The parameters a_i can be found in the appendix.

Another challenge is the variable contact pressure, which cannot be modelled by fretting fatigue tests. On the one hand, this variable pressure is already taken into account in the strength hypothesis. On the other hand, some representative pressures such as the mean value or the maximum are initially assumed and the accuracy is checked for the tribological effect.

FIGURE 3 a) Empirical function for fretting fatigue limit from fretting pad experiments from Knabner [2], b) distribution of corresponding fretting fatigue limit at the bearing seat

RESULTS

Experimental results

The bending fatigue strength was determined on 7 specimens using the staircase method and the evaluation results in a bearable nominal stress amplitude of 154 MPa related to the shaft diameter. The corresponding experiments are showed in FIGURE 4.

σ_a (MPa)	F (Nm)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
162	23611					x			
155	22590		x		o		x		
149	21716	o		o				o	
cycles in 10^3		10 000	3 762	10 000	10 000	5 339	4 896	10 000	

154 MPa F

FIGURE 4 Staircase results of the 3-point rotating bending tests with shaft from C45+N

The analysis of the fracture surface shows a typical course of a shaft loaded by rotating bending (FIGURE 5). Starting from the crack nucleus, the crack propagates around the circumference of the shaft. Axial position of the cracks is in the area between $x = 2 \dots 5$ mm.

FIGURE 5 a) Rupture at 162 MPa after $5.34 \cdot 10^6$ cycles, b) run out at load amplitude 149 MPa

Numerical results

FIGURE 6 shows the distribution of contact pressure and slip at one point in the revolution in the rolled-out representation. The influence of the rolling elements on the pressure can be clearly recognised. The maxima occur at the contact edge, where the shaft surface presses against it due to the compression. The corresponding axial slip understandably occurs on the opposite bending tension side. The tangential slip plays a subordinate role, whereby the characteristic includes an irreversible slip component that leads to bearing creep. The role of the travelling movement for the strength assessment is subordinate. Only the associated amplification of the axial slip, which favours damage in this case, should be mentioned here.

FIGURE 6 Pressure and slip distribution over the bearing seat contact

FIGURE 7 shows an example of the pressure and slip curve at the potential failure point, at position $x = 4$ mm. In contrast to laboratory tests on fretting pads, the contact pressure is observed to vary over time. This is subsequently abstracted for the definition of fretting fatigue $\sigma_{FF}(s_a, p)$ as maximum, mean and minimum pressure. The corresponding axial amplitude is approximately $s_a = 7 \mu\text{m}$. To calculate the fretting fatigue strength $\sigma_{FF}(s_a, p)$, the locally prevailing slip state in the tangential and axial directions is determined using the root summation.

FIGURE 7 Pressure and axial slip over load rotations at crack initiation point

Fatigue calculations

The critical state for the C45+N steel analysed here is at a contact pressure of $p \approx 40$ MPa and a slip amplitude of $s_a \approx 10 \mu\text{m}$. The corresponding strength was $\sigma_{FF, worst} = 122$ MPa according to Knabner [2]. As can be seen, the equivalent stress is more or less above this value (FIGURE 8). The criterion according to McDiarmid shows the lowest stress, while Findley is positioned between the other closely arranged criteria.

FIGURE 8 Results of equivalent stresses compared to the local fretting fatigue limits along the component interface

The adjustment of the strength criterion according to EQUATION (10) shows that the edge areas in which the crack occurs are particularly relevant for the integral criteria and for QCP (FIGURE 8). These criteria also score best in the benchmarks recorded. However, it can also be seen that here the equivalent stresses exceed the fretting fatigue limit, only for the abstraction of the contact pressure in the minimum expression shows no overload. However, it should be noted that higher stress states can occur in the numerics at the contact edges due to singularity. A treatment of these questions is planned for future detailed analyses. The abstraction of the variable contact pressure towards lower mean pressures is plausible, since the contact pressure decrease, the high axial slip and also the highest local stress prevail simultaneously on the tensile bending side.

SUMMARY

Extensive fatigue tests were carried out to determine the influences on contact fatigue in rolling bearing seats. Firstly, the shaft material was C45+N, which was analysed in a 3-point rotating bending test in the HCF domain.

Due to the strong multiaxial stress state, current multiaxial strength criteria of the integral stress and critical plane method were used for the evaluation. In addition, the fretting fatigue was defined according to preliminary works as a function of the local pressure and slip.

The results show that the integral criteria SIH and BO and the QCP match the crack location relatively well. Due to the crack propagation, there are small uncertainties with regard to the exact crack location. However, it can be seen that the variable pressure for the present case can be abstracted as an average pressure in order to be able to apply the method presented and to transfer the laboratory characteristic values determined in preliminary works to the component level.

For future developments, other shaft materials from the wind energy sector have already been analysed and the evaluation using these methods is pending. Due to the edge effects, the method of critical distances is also to be tested for more precise strength assessment. The influence of the bearing type as well as the internal pressure and bearing ring thickness is also of interest, as they represent important parameters for the output in the contact stress due to the modified stiffnesses.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

a	Material parameter
b	Material parameter
c	Material parameter
d	Material parameter
l	Interference
l_j	Shrink fit joining length
f_{-1}	Fatigue limit at bending
s_{-1}	Reverse fatigue limit ($R = -1$) at normal load, amplitude
s_0	Repeating fatigue limit ($R = 0$) at normal load, maximal value
t_{-1}	Reverse fatigue limit ($R = -1$) at shear load, amplitude
t_0	Repeating fatigue limit ($R = 0$) at shear load, maximal value
C	Shear stress in a material plane
N	Normal stress on material plane
ξ	Interference related to diameter according to DIN 743 $\xi = l / d$
σ_{ba}	Nominal bending amplitude
σ_{eq}	Equivalent stress amplitude
σ_{UTS}	Ultimate stress
σ_Y	Yield stress

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Funk W., *Der Einfluß der Reibkorrosion auf die Dauerhaltbarkeit zusammengesetzter Maschinenelemente*, Darmstadt, 1968.
- (2) Knabner D., Hauschild S., Suchý L., Vetter S., Leidich E., Hasse A., *Int. Journal of Fatigue*, Vol. 165, 2022, 108209
- (3) DIN, *DIN 50100*, 2016
- (4) Rennert R, Kullig E, Vormwald M, Esderts A, Luke M., *Analytical Strength Assessment 7th. Ed.*, VDMA, 2021.
- (5) Papuga J., *Int. J. of Fatigue*, Vol. 33, 2011, pp. 153–65
- (6) Papuga J., Nesládek M., Hasse A., Cízová E., Suchý L., *Metals*, Vol. 12, 2022, pp. 289.
- (7) Liu J, Zenner H., *European Structural Integrity Society*, Vol. 31, 2003, pp. 147–64
- (8) Böhme S. A., Vinogradov A., Papuga J., Berto F., *FFEMS*, Vol. 44, 2021, pp. 2033-53
- (9) Findley W.N., *Journal of Engineering for Industry*, Vol. 81, 1959, pp. 301–5
- (10) McDiarmid DL, *FFEMS*, Vol. 17, 1994, pp. 1475–84
- (11) Papuga J, Halama R., *Archive of Applied Mechanics*, 2018

APPENDIX

Fretting fatigue parameters

$$a_0 = 1,031$$

$$a_1 = -7,113 \cdot \exp^{-3}$$

$$a_2 = -2,624 \cdot \exp^{-2}$$

$$a_3 = 3,472 \cdot \exp^{-4}$$

$$a_4 = -1,278 \cdot \exp^{-3}$$

$$a_5 = 7,462 \cdot \exp^{-4}$$

$$a_6 = 8,596 \cdot \exp^{-5}$$

$$a_7 = -4,787 \cdot \exp^{-6}$$

$$a_8 = -5,343 \cdot \exp^{-6}$$

$$a_9 = 0,9224$$

$$a_{10} = -8,696 \cdot \exp^{-2}$$

$$a_{11} = 7,489 \cdot \exp^{-5}$$

$$a_{12} = 4,84 \cdot \exp^{-3}$$

$$a_{13} = -5,617 \cdot \exp^{-6}$$